

New theory: the PIE root *dheh1 “to do; to put, to place, to set” derives from the earlier meanings “to fit together, to press together”, in turn from “to make firm<firm”

Alexandru Gheorghiu

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Since mid 2022 I have been trying to figure from whence the meanings “to do; to put, to place, to set” arose in the Proto-Indo-European root **d^heh₁*-, “to do; to put, to place, to set” (there is another PIE root **d^heh₁*- meaning “to suck” which I will discuss in this paper as well).

After trying out a number of scenarios (and publishing drafts in the autumn of 2022 wherein I described some of those), I have come to the conclusion that the earlier meaning was “to fit together”, from an earlier meaning “to press together”: I got the idea after I saw the etymology of Old Armenian *arnem* (which meant “to make, do, form, produce, compose, operate, act, render, commit, effectuate, execute, cause”) as deriving from PIE **h₂er-* “to fit, to fix, to put together, to join, to slot”, +*-ū(-n-)*. The aorist stem *արար-* (*arar-*) is a reduplication of the same root. Cognate with [Ancient Greek ἀραρίσκω](#) (*ararískō*, “to join, fit together”) (imperfect [ἤραρον](#) (*ḗraron*), perfect [ἄραρα](#) (*árara*); compare [արարի](#) (*arari*, “I did”) and [արարայ](#) (*araray*, “I was done”) and [Avestan](#) (*ərənāvi*, “he was created”).

That’s actually a fitting way to think of “doing” and a good way to think of “making”: when you make something, you are usually putting things together (including thoughts and ideas); from “to make” developed the meaning “to do”, a trivial development.

Thinking about it for a second, I realized that in addition to the meanings “to do, to make” deriving so easily from such earlier meanings, so do the meanings “to set, to put, to place”: when one places/puts something, like a book on a table, you bring the book together with the table.

From a recent paper by the linguist Michiel de Vann I take the idea that PIE **d^heh₁-* “to suck” derives from PIE **d^heh₁-* “to put, to place, to set”; either via the way he proposes: placing the baby’s mouth at the nipple; or, as I prefer and as I posit, (based on his theory, adapting it) from the baby’s lips clasp upon the nipple, from the earlier meaning “to fit together<to press together”.

Thus I propose that for both PIE **d^heh₁-*, “to do; to put, to place, to set” and for PIE **d^heh₁-* “to suck”, the earlier Pre-PIE meanings were “to put together, to fit together”, and I think that those meanings were in turn from “to press together, to compact, to make firm”, in turn from “firm”.

Compare PIE **d^her-* “to hold”, from which derives Latin *firmus* meaning “firm, strong, steadfast, enduring, stable”; PIE **d^herǵ^h-* “to bind fast; be firm; support; strong, robust”. PIE **d^heh₁-*, in its Pre-PIE root-meanings, is probably the source of both PIE **d^her-* “to hold” and PIE **d^herǵ^h-* “to bind fast; be firm; support; strong, robust”, and the source of PIE **d^heu*, “to press; to strangle”.

Another PIE root, PIE **d^heu*, “to flow, to run”, suggests to me that the oldest meaning was “force; strength; power”, from whence derived “to flow, to run” and, via a different pathway, “firm” and from there “to make firm, to press”> “to fit together”> “to put together” and so on as I described above.

A. G., January 9th, 2024